

Appendix

CO₂ and CH₄ emissions of rewetted peatlands considered for our review. As a starting point, we used the survey of Wilson, Blain, et al., (2016), who collated existing peatland rewetting studies as an update of the tier 1 emission factors of the IPCC Wetlands supplement. This collection was further supplemented by studies published after 2016. In order to tailor the data set to the requirements of our study, we imposed additional selection criteria to those raised by Wilson, Blain, et al., (2016):

- both, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions must be available for a site, as the RF modelling is based on the site-specific proportion of both fluxes.
- studied peatlands must have a drainage and rewetting history. We omitted pristine sites as they may differ in major ecological features, such as vegetation, hydrology and geochemistry from their rewetted counterparts with a drainage history (Kreyling et al., 2021).
- CO₂ and CH₄ emissions must be reported at the ecosystem level. Emissions must therefore either have been measured directly on an ecosystem scale using the eddy covariance approach or must have been upscaled accordingly from point-scale chamber measurements.
- mean annual water level must be at least 30 cm below ground. This excludes peatlands that are technically deemed abandoned and/or restored, but do not meet the hydrological preconditions to halt further peat decay and CO₂ emissions.
- reported CO₂ and CH₄ emissions must be based on in-situ measurements, as modelling studies by their nature tend to reproduce reported data and their incorporation may produce redundancy.

Our literature survey added up to a total of 46 site-years. Following Wilson, Blain, et al., (2016), seasonal budgets were extrapolated to the annual scale using a conversion factor of 1.15 for CH₄ and 1.15 for ecosystem respiration, assuming that off-season photosynthesis is zero (Saarnio et al., 2007). Water level is reported as mean annual water level in cm above surface level with positive signs indicating inundation.

Study	Measurement Year	Mean Annual Water Level	Peatland Type	Climate Zone	Current Land Use	Previous Land Use	Measurement Method	NEE season (g CO ₂ m ⁻²)	NEE annual (g CO ₂ m ⁻²)	CH ₄ season (g CH ₄ m ⁻²)	CH ₄ annual (g CH ₄ m ⁻²)
Augustin & Chojnicki, 2008	2005	30	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC	NA	-1,833	NA	252.1
Augustin & Chojnicki, 2008	2006	30	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC	NA	184	NA	493.3
Augustin & Chojnicki, 2008	2007	30	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC	NA	36	NA	237.6
Beetz et al., 2013	2008	-30	Bog	Temperate	ExtGrassland	Grassland	CC	NA	0	NA	2.0
D' Acunha et al., 2019	NA	-2	Bog	Boreal	None	PeatExtract	EC	NA	-213	NA	17.0
Drösler, 2005	NA	45	Bog	Temperate	None	PeatExtract	CC	NA	704	NA	2.0
Drösler, 2005	NA	-5	Bog	Temperate	None	PeatExtract	CC	NA	227	NA	2.7
Drösler, 2005	NA	-12	Bog	Temperate	None	PeatExtract	CC	NA	466	NA	9.3
Hemes et al., 2018	NA	NA	Fen	Sub-Tropical	None	Agriculture	EC	NA	1,188	NA	61.3
Hemes et al., 2018	NA	NA	Fen	Sub-Tropical	None	Agriculture	EC	NA	-1,177	NA	42.7
Hemes et al., 2018	NA	NA	Fen	Sub-Tropical	None	Agriculture	EC	NA	-818	NA	66.7
Hemes et al., 2018	NA	NA	Fen	Sub-Tropical	None	Agriculture	EC	NA	-1,665	NA	60.0
Hendriks et al., 2007	2005	-10	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC	NA	-1,140	NA	41.3
Hendriks et al., 2007	2006	-10	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC	NA	-851	NA	42.7
Herbst et al., 2013	2009	NA	Fen	Temperate	ExtGrassland	Agriculture	EC	NA	-983	NA	11.0
Herbst et al., 2013	2010	NA	Fen	Temperate	ExtGrassland	Agriculture	EC	NA	-195	NA	14.0
Herbst et al., 2013	2011	NA	Fen	Temperate	ExtGrassland	Agriculture	EC	NA	-387	NA	17.0
Kandel et al., 2019, 2020; Karki et al., 2019	NA	7	Fen	Oceanic	None	Grassland	CC	NA	807	NA	53.0
Kandel et al., 2019, 2020; Karki et al., 2019	2015/2016	-1	Fen	Oceanic	Paludiculture	Agriculture	CC	NA	345	NA	81.3
Kandel et al., 2019, 2020; Karki et al., 2019	2015/2016	-1	Fen	Oceanic	Paludiculture	Agriculture	CC	NA	213	NA	116.0
Kandel et al., 2019, 2020; Karki et al., 2019	2016/2017	-3	Fen	Oceanic	Paludiculture	Agriculture	CC	NA	763	NA	34.7
Kandel et al., 2019, 2020; Karki et al., 2019	2016/2017	0	Fen	Oceanic	Paludiculture	Agriculture	CC	NA	678	NA	69.3

Knox et al., 2015	NA	100	Fen	Sub-Tropical	None	Agriculture	EC	NA	-1,349	NA	70.7
Knox et al., 2015	NA	25	Fen	Sub-Tropical	None	Agriculture	EC	NA	-1,456	NA	52.0
Koebisch et al., 2020	2014	30	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	EC	NA	283	NA	53.0
Koebisch et al., 2020	2015	30	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	EC	NA	823	NA	40.0
Koebisch et al., 2020	2016	30	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	EC	NA	347	NA	44.0
Koebisch et al., 2020	2017	0	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	EC	NA	65	NA	40.0
Poyda et al., 2016	2012/2013	-11	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC	NA	1,430	NA	13.7
Poyda et al., 2016	2013/2014	-11	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC	NA	623	NA	3.6
Renou-Wilson et al., 2016	NA	-14	Fen	Oceanic	None	Grassland	CC	NA	-293	NA	4.5
Renou-Wilson et al., 2016	NA	-14	Fen	Oceanic	None	Grassland	CC	NA	4	NA	7.2
Renou-Wilson et al., 2016	NA	-9	Fen	Oceanic	ExtGrassland	Grassland	CC	NA	315	NA	12.0
Renou-Wilson et al., 2016	NA	-10	Fen	Oceanic	ExtGrassland	Grassland	CC	NA	312	NA	12.7
Schaller et al., 2022	2017	5	Bog	Temperate	None	PeatExtract	EC	NA	72	NA	8.7
Schrier-Uijl et al., 2014	2005	25	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC, EC	NA	-1,000	NA	19.1
Schrier-Uijl et al., 2014	2006	25	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC, EC	NA	-1,000	NA	20.5
Schrier-Uijl et al., 2014	2007	25	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC, EC	NA	-1,900	NA	19.8
Schrier-Uijl et al., 2014	2008	25	Fen	Temperate	None	Grassland	CC, EC	NA	-1,500	NA	17.6
Strack & Zuback, 2013	NA	-26,25	Bog	Boreal	None	PeatExtract	CC	-110	-42	5.3	6.1
Tuittila et al., 1999, 2000	1995	-11	Bog	Boreal	None	PeatExtract	CC	161	271	1.5	1.7
Tuittila et al., 1999, 2000	1996	-11	Bog	Boreal	None	PeatExtract	CC	95	205	1.8	2.1
Tuittila et al., 1999, 2000	1996	9	Bog	Boreal	None	PeatExtract	CC	-33	77	2.7	3.0
Tuittila et al., 1999, 2000	1997	-14	Bog	Boreal	None	PeatExtract	CC	143	253	2.0	2.3
Tuittila et al., 1999, 2000	1997	7	Bog	Boreal	None	PeatExtract	CC	-238	-128	4.8	5.5

Wilson et al., 2016	NA	6	Bog	Oceanic	None	PeatExtract	CC	NA	-381	NA	12.0
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